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The Alternative Food Geography in Europe: An Elaboration Through the Socio-Metabolic Approach

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Abstract: This study applies the socio-metabolic approach and relatedly the concept of planetary urbanization understanding to detect the identity of the “alternative zones” embedded in the food supply chain of cities (FSC). To achieve shortened and sustainable FSCs for cities, strong alternative food networks (AFNs) should be developed and sustained. The precious element of a strong AFN is its urban areas, which serve as niche alternative food initiatives (AFIs) for sustainability transitions in food supply chains (FSCs). To achieve shorter and more sustainable FSCs in cities, it is crucial to develop and sustain empowered alternative food networks (AFNs) by deploying their AFIs. Within this context, this study examines AFIs in 12 European FUSILLI cities to understand the potential of the intrinsic AFN to accelerate the sustainable transition in FSCs. Considering the results of AFNs in accelerating sustainability transitions in FSCs. Results through spatial analyses of food ecosystems of FUSILLI cities, although there are prominent examples with a strong short and alternative food network, it is obvious that the sustainable transition into an alternative food network has proceeded; however, the analysis of AFNs in FUSILLI cities demonstrates that sustainability transitions have advanced through vigorous AFNs. However, extended urban areas still have room to supersede their place in conventional/industrial agricultural production, which remains embedded in these spaces. The same inference applies to urban–rural linkages, which need to be strengthened to support the relocation of the food system in the development of AFNs in urban areas and to create more sustainable and shortened FSCs. Also, it is obvious that cities with greater extended AFNs, for example, Rome, due to its great number of AFIs and geographical extent of AFN covering concentrated urban areas and to strengthen the rural–urban linkage for shortened food supply chains, as well as extended urban areas, and Oslo, due to its great variety of AFIs embedded in concentrated urban areas with alternative food production areas in its (erstwhile rural areas) extended urban areas.

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1. Introduction

In the last century, the representation of settlement systems has been identified as crystallized formations of urban, peri-urban, and rural areas. “Urban” was described as a settlement which has a form, border, and includes non-agricultural activities. “Rural” was areas that have concrete borders and include agricultural activities within peasant communities and agricultural areas. In between these, peri-urban (or, in some conceptualizations, peri-rural) areas indicate areas that both locate urban and rural facilities and activities and, in some cases, areas allocated for further urban development and urban sprawl.

However, the urban–rural dichotomy has been invalid in understanding, to interpret, and developing policies for settlement systems, regional systems, and urban economics since the 1980s. The possibility of drawing borders between urban and rural areas has been disappearing, and the rural areas are covered with urban footprints [1]. The relationship between rural and urban areas is changing, and the rural–urban divide is fading, as there is an increase in the flow of people, goods, and services between urban and rural areas as well as newly emerging migration and livelihood patterns [2]. The demarcation of city boundaries and the inherited categories, such as rural–urban divisions, are no longer sufficient to explain the realities of 21st-century capitalist urban development [3–6]. Also, defining the geography according to an urban–rural divide and simplifying “urban” as a place of a “city” are a city-centric approach [7].

The current discussion in urban theory reformulates this conceptualization, especially since the beginning of the 21st century. As “non-urban” spaces are being deeply transformed in relation to the capitalist spatial development in the world and are undergoing a drastic restructuring [4], the most dramatic change occurs in the transformation of the erstwhile “peri-urban”. According to Brenner and Schmid (2015), the expansion of industrial agriculture, as well as changes in land uses to facilitate resource extraction in rural and peri-urban areas, needs expressions of capitalist urbanization. The wildest parts of the world, rural areas, protected sites, and all the out-of-urban areas are also in the process of capitalist urbanization in the context of serving urban areas (spatial agglomerations) through mining activities, infrastructure, and so on. Examining recent trends reveals that a new planetary formation of urbanization is superseding inherited urban narratives [5]. So, under the concept of planetary urbanization, “urban” moments and functions are not only concentrated in cities but also take place in non-city spaces that are exposed to socioeconomic, infrastructural, and socioecological transformation [8]. Such transformation aims at supporting the socioeconomic needs and dynamics of metropolitan cities and agglomerations. Therefore, in the conceptualization of planetary urbanization, there are two types of spaces: city spaces and non-city spaces. Non-city spaces are identified as those producing and serving city spaces [9,10]. This operationalization of non-city spaces facilitates capitalist industrialization not only within densely populated cities but also in near and distant zones [4].

In this study, we aim to operationalize the socio-metabolic approach with a focus on the metabolic input of food by using the AFIs as the unit of analysis. To operationalize the approach, we spatially analyze the distribution and location choice of AFIs under five categories: alternative (i) production, (ii) consumption, (iii) distribution and procurement, (iv) governance, and (v) waste initiatives of the food system of 12 FUSILLI cities. By doing so, we detect “alternative zones” that can be empowered for sustainability transitions in terms of food production and procurement. Relying on this approach, this study focuses on the alternative food networks (AFNs); therefore, the potential transitions through short(er) food supply chains (SFSCs) of cities are focused. This study also aims to fill the gap in the literature, which is the operationalization of socio-metabolic approaches to benefit its holistic view of “food” as a metabolic input and to understand the role of urban places in building AFNs. The following discussions resolve the conceptualizations of planetary urbanization, the socio-metabolic approach, and their treatment of the metabolic input of food, urban and rural geography, and urbanization processes for a better understanding of the mentioned gap in the literature.

1.1. The Planetary Understanding of Urbanization Processes

Planetary urbanization, as an intellectual approach, aims to develop a new understanding of emergent urban conditions and ongoing urban transformations all around the globe. Although spatial agglomerations remain important within urbanization processes,

urbanization goes beyond them, extending through erstwhile peri-urban and rural areas by persistent transformations across the world. The planetary understanding attempts to conceptualize contemporary urbanization holistically and looks beyond spatial agglomerations. Rooted in Lefebvre's "implosion-explosion" conceptualization, the planetary view conceives urbanization as a series of multifaceted processes constituted through three moment types: (1) concentrated urbanization; (2) extended urbanization; and (3) differential urbanization, which is mutually and dialectically constituted moments [5]. This analytical distinction provides a new epistemological basis to reinvent a broad conceptualization of urbanization, going beyond either fixed spatial units (cities) or mere agglomeration spaces.

Rather than city-centric or agglomeration-based approaches to urbanization, the planetary view describes new, intertwined moments of urbanization processes. Concentrated urbanization refers to spatial agglomerations of population, means of production, infrastructure, and investment. Extended urbanization describes the operationalization and transformation of places—territories far from the dense population centers—through socioeconomic, infrastructural, and socio-metabolic metamorphoses. Extended urbanization produces a subsequent uneven thickening and stretching of the urban fabric. The historical and contemporary geographies of urban restructuring and transformation encompass broad landscapes and territories, including massive socio-metabolic metamorphoses that often support distant spatial agglomerations. For this reason, the moment of concentrated urbanization is inextricably connected to that of extended urbanization. The processes of concentrated and extended urbanization are intertwined with the process of differential urbanization, through which inherited socio-spatial configurations are continually destroyed and reproduced in relation to the broader developmental dynamics of modern capitalism [5].

The selected conceptualization lets us understand the dimensions of the settlement system and the society living in this settlement system in a wide manner that inputs such as food are factors to analyze and to resolve the socio-metabolic system that operates between and among these three spatial categories, namely concentrated urbanization, extended urbanization, and differential urbanization. Brenner and Schmid ([5]; p. 171) made such categorization that can provide further input for the long-term urban food planning to cities that it provides an insight into urban planning, land allocation, zoning, and a combination of land practices in the planning system and decision making mechanisms.

1.2. The Socio-Metabolic Approach

Relying on the planetary urbanization approach, one of the major contemporary counterpoints to the city-centric approach to consider the ongoing socio-spatial transformation and metabolic degradation is socio-metabolic approach [11]. In this approach, spatial agglomerations (cities) are supported by diverse metabolic inputs such as food, water, labor, materials, fuel, and so on, and endanger various byproducts such as waste, pollution, and carbon. The majority of these byproducts are produced and then absorbed in non-city spaces through the consumption processes of city spaces. For instance, industrialized agriculture or agribusiness has the most human-induced effects on the ecosystem as it emits a quarter of greenhouse gas emissions [12]. The agglomerations in this perspective are exemplified by land enclosure, industrial agriculture, deforestation, waste processing, ecological load displacement, etc. In this recent approach that departs from planetary urbanization, spatial agglomerations are part of a bigger socio-metabolic (transformation) flow, including social, political, material, infrastructural, and ecological moments.

For a sustainable food system, the United Nations and international organizations suggest a shift in economic, social, and environmental dimensions [13]. The United Nations 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) also promotes the resilience

of food systems, safe and resilient food systems for especially vulnerable groups, and reducing food waste along the food production and supply chain [14] as it is still compromising of industrialized agriculture and capitalist productions [15,16]. The traditional urban food system is still dependent on rural areas for production and is emphasized by the capitalist way of processing and distributing the food, degrading the food security and resilience of food systems [14]. Considering these recent challenges and development, our attempt to operationalize the socio-metabolic approach [11] to reinvestigate urban, peri-urban, and rural interlinkages in terms of intrinsic alternative food supply chains (AFSCs) embedded in urban areas by examining the spatial distribution of AFIs (alternative food initiatives) and distance-based spatial density of AFIs (geographical proximity) through the urban geographies (concentrated, extended and differential) of cities fulfill the gap of food, socio-metabolic approach and its relational operations in cities in the literature.

Based on the research held in the scope of the project, this study attempts to re-conceptualize urban, rural, peri-urban, and their interlinkages by using AFIs in 12 European cities by using the power of the socio-metabolic approach. Since the urbanization processes are not only limited to the city itself and are operated by capitalist development [11], this approach also comes up with a powerful conceptualization to understand the commodification of food as a material input and food supply chains (FSCs) embedded within urban areas and unfolding interlinks of these urbanization moments.

Socio-metabolic approach brings out a new conceptualization of urban, peri-urban, and rural relationships associated with emergent geographies and socio-ecological flow of planetary urbanization [11]. Rather than city-centric approaches [13], urbanization is conceived as the flow of social and metabolic inputs and outputs accelerated by capitalist development. In other words, to apply the current discussions and conceptualizations for settlement systems beyond urban, peri-urban, and rural areas identification, we used the socio-metabolic approach, which defines food as a metabolic input in urbanization processes.

The socio-metabolic approach acknowledges the settlement system as a socio-metabolic process in which food is an input. Since food is a globally traded product and produced in huge amounts (industrial mode of food supply) in rural areas via persistent restructuring through land enclosure, dispossession, etc., the rural is no longer erstwhile “rural”, it is rather an extended urbanized area via stretching and thickening of the “city”. These areas rather consist of conventional agricultural practices and activities to serve cities, as in waste disposal, energy production, communication infrastructure, mining activities, and so on. Considering food as a metabolic input and globally traded product, this study examines the potential of urban areas to sustain an alternative and sustainable urban food network (ASFNs).

1.3. The Operational Data and 12 FUSILLI Cities

The data gathered in this study and the methodology developed through the FUSILLI project, which is funded by the EU Horizon 2020 Programme Programme (This article depends primarily on the research done at FUSILLI project, specifically Task 3.4. Urban and Rural Links- Specific Policies and Actions. FUSILLI project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101000717). The FUSILLI project focuses on supporting 12 project cities (Kharkiv, San Sebastián, Kolding, Oslo, Tampere, Differdange, Turin, Rome, Castelo Branco, Nilüfer (Bursa), Rijeka, and Athens, as they are the application areas of the FUSILLI project’s LLs as partner cities) to facilitate their transition towards more sustainable urban food systems. The 12 FUSILLI cities let this research showcase a holistic European context that cities have a balanced geographical distribution in Europe and in different European countries. Also, the FUSILLI cities include major metropolitan capital cities such

as Oslo, Athens, Rome, and Kharkiv; middle-range cities such as Turin, San Sebastian, Tampere, and Nilüfer; and small-scale cities, which are Differdange, Rijeka, Castelo Branco, and Kolding.

2. The Alternatives: Scope, Variations, and the Short Chain

The FUSILLI project aims to develop an urban food planning framework for cities through the implementation of living labs (LLs) in each partner city. One of the main goals of the project is to ensure that cities adopt sustainable agri-food systems across all sectors, including production, consumption, distribution, processing, waste management, and governance. In this context, alternative food networks (AFNs)—as grassroots innovations, implementation areas, and scientific research fields—help us understand the potential of cities to develop policies and actions for shorter FSCs. AFNs are usually opted as “more natural”, “healthier”, and “local” [17]. AFNs and alternative food initiatives (AFIs) encourage new and emerging actors within the mainstream food regime as transformative engines while introducing new values, expressions, and sustainable solutions for urban, regional, and local food systems. With the involvement of producers, consumers, co-producers, and various civil society actors, AFNs represent a novel and innovative grassroots movement as a form of niche movement offering practical solutions to achieve sustainable food systems [17–20].

A sustainable food system should be able to provide nourishment for people, enhance social and economic sustainability, and have minimal to positive effects on the environment [17,21]. SDG of the United Nations 2030 agenda also promotes the optimization of food systems from unsustainable forms to sustainable goals in food systems to reduce food inequalities and nutrition, food insecurity, environmental degradation, and food sovereignty [17]. Moreover, since the COVID-19 pandemic, food insecurity and resilience of urban food systems have become more worrisome, and it is likely to face new challenges in urban food systems as urbanization, population increase, and migration of populations due—but not limited to war—experienced such as in Syria and Ukraine, epidemics and pandemics influencing and changing consumer behavior as well [14]. Under these circumstances, researchers put forward local levels to accommodate inclusive and sustainable food systems [14,22]. Food produced within local food systems, as well as the systems themselves, are frequently regarded as sustainable. This perception of improved environmental sustainability is largely due to the reduction in food miles, which in turn leads to lower greenhouse gas emissions [17]. In the shed of new planetary challenges and forces upon food, AFNs serve as an inclusive term that describes newly emerging networks of producers, consumers, and related actors who provide alternatives to the unsustainable industrial model of food supply [23]. This umbrella term encompasses a variety of initiatives challenging conventional food systems. Whatmore, Stassart, and Renting [24] describe AFNs as a series of distinct collective movements that include organic production, fair trade networks, artisanal networks, local or regional initiatives, and urban agricultural projects. Additionally, AFIs are often characterized by their connections to social movements advocating for environmental sustainability, sustainable agriculture, rural social justice, or consumer health and safety [25]. They also emphasize the “resocialization” and “re-spatialization” of food systems [26].

AFNs’ defining traits include small-scale production, local community engagement, food quality for safe consumption, personal or informal relationships built on trust, organic farming practices, focus on welfare, and the use of unconventional sales and logistics methods. Primarily, food safety issues have been at the core of consumer trust and quality turn discussions on AFN literature in the last two decades. More recent research on food safety issues in food circulation during COVID-19 [14] also reveals that safe, eco-friendly, and organic food has led to a surge in direct sales and alternative food networks

[12]. Despite the overall concept of AFNs, it is important to note that although this does not apply to all AFNs, in the literature, there are instances where unfair and discriminatory access to food [27] can be observed, especially when industrialized methods of food procurement and global practices are used [25], even though the food is produced locally. Although AFNs may be producing organic/biodynamic/agroecological food, they may also be using conventional agricultural models and selling to consumers from long distances through tourism or commercial private firms [27], which results in increasing Greenhouse Gas emissions, causing further environmental pollution.

AFNs can vary based on socioeconomic, cultural, and geographical factors [12]. Horlings and Marsden [28] broaden the scope of AFNs by describing them as complex networks of viable economic activities that utilize ecological resources in efficient and sustainable ways. According to this perspective, key elements of ecological modernization include qualitative production and consumption, economic growth aligned with ecological goals, modern technologies that reduce environmental impacts, a proactive governmental role, and strong community-building efforts (e.g., capacity building and awareness raising). Within this framework, AFNs contribute to sustaining urban food systems, aligning closely with the goals of the FUSILLI project.

The AFN, as an implementation area and an academic research field, has subconceptualizations and practice fields, which are local food systems (localized or relocalized and abbreviated as LFS), short(er) food supply chains (SFSC), new nested markets, new peasantries, and civic food networks (CFN). The first practice area of AFN, the local food systems (LFSs), give strong links to the geographical proximity of specialized farms, social proximity of public and private entities in the territory, social proximity of food-processing units, and networks of distribution [19,20], as well as re-definition of the role of small and micro scale firms in agriculture and food commodity chains [29]. With reference to linking territorial strategies and specifications, LFS operationalizes “territorial proximity”, to include “geographical proximity” and “organizational proximity”.

SFSCs (as well as AFSCs) are defined as the forms of producer and consumer resistance examples against the globalization of food systems of whom depending international trade primarily relies on long distance-based and multi-actor faceted supply chains [30,31]. In this respect, SFSCs are thought to be a very proper tool for organic producers, sustainable production, and ecological production or locally produced specific products considering the life cycle approach as well as convenience for the benefit of small-holders [16,32]. Basically, it provides geographical and territorial proximity of food distribution and aims at bypassing intermediaries or middlemen and the direct procurement of food from producer to consumer. The concept of proximity takes significant importance in SFSC and is composed of geographical proximity, social proximity, and economic proximity [27,33]. Geographical proximity arises as the key dimension for the measurement of distance, while social proximity expresses proximity within the relations of producer and consumer as a trust-dependent relation. Building relations within a community through trustworthy consumers and advanced eco-friendly production methods boosts socioeconomic effects [17]. Economic proximity is directly related to the locality debate, which states that money circulates within a local community in this system. At the 141st plenary session of the European Committee of the Regions, which was held in December 2020, a European framework to be established for promoting and strengthening short supply chains based on innovative practices adopted successfully at the local level was called [34]. Also, the SFSC has gained attention as a policy need for a lower dependency in the global FSC with the crises of the COVID-19 pandemic and the Ukraine crisis [14,35,36].

3. Materials and Methods

All the while, there is a need to conduct a comprehensive, area-specific, and long-term evaluation that examines the entire lifecycle of FSCs and monitors both producers' and consumers' behaviors to gain a clearer understanding of the effects of local initiatives [16]. To achieve an SFSC by precise actions, it is important to assess the current situation of the food system, the origin of the food (as an attribute of re-spatialization of food), the distribution systems relation and face-to-face potential (as an attribute of resocialization of the food). By revealing the AFIs and combining it with current land use, it is possible to comprehend the potential of cities for building SFSC development. In this respect, this study has performed a socio-metabolic approach to determine erstwhile urban, peri-urban and rural areas with respect to the distribution of alternative food systems. The mentioned socio-metabolic approach provides us with a conceptualization of the settlement system with categories of concentrated, extended, and differentiated urban areas materialized under contemporary capitalism. We identify AFNs to operationalize the approach in relation to SFSC, and we defined the geography of AFN in 12 FUSILLI cities, representing the proximity of AFN over extended and concentrated urban areas.

3.1. The Data

Since food is one of the metabolic inputs within urbanization processes and it has been a globally traded product, this conceptualization provides us to deduce the current situation of alternative flow of food distribution and production spaces within the food supply chain (FSC) of cities. We made a specific and novel design and categorization to reveal AFNs of FUSILLI cities under the five pillars of the project: production, consumption, governance, distribution/processing, and waste. Also, to understand the consumption preferences of the cities, we included "conventional consumption", which includes supermarkets, bazaars, shops, etc. Therefore, the alternative food-related spaces are comprehended and subcategorized under six main categories as:

- alternative production spaces;
- alternative procurement, distribution, and processing spaces;
- conventional consumption spaces;
- alternative consumption spaces;
- alternative waste management spaces;
- alternative governance spaces.

To understand the current situation of AFNs and FSCs in FUSILLI Cities, we developed research that collects main food product groups and the food miles for these products consumed in cities. We have detailed the types of initiatives and organizations under these headings and added explanations for cities to understand the context for each type of initiative, e.g., consumer cooperative, ecology collective, buyers' club, etc. The spatial distribution of these initiatives under these headings are firstly detected in Google Earth for each city in KMZ format and then processed in ArcGIS 10.8 by converting to shapefile as digital points representing the locations of AFIs' categories and associated with the CORINE land use database (The Copernicus Land Monitoring Service is jointly implemented by the European Environmental Agency—which coordinates the European component—and the DG Joint Research Centre of the European Commission—who coordinates the global component. Available at <https://land.copernicus.eu/en/products/corine-land-cover/clc2018> and accessed on 27 May 2022).

3.2. Analysis by Geographical Information System

The methodology to assess the extent of AFNs and the potential to develop shortened FSC of cities relies on geoprocessing (spatial distribution) analysis and further distance-based spatial point density analysis of AFIs in the ArcGIS platform. To understand spatial distribution across the urbanization moments, the spatial distribution (geoprocessing analysis) of AFIs is done in the ArcGIS environment across the land use of cities using CORINE dataset. Urbanization moments of concentrated, extended, and differential urbanized areas are comprehended by re-categorized mapping of CORINE land use data into three mentioned urbanization moments.

3.3. Socio-Metabolic Methodology

The CORINE land use data is re-categorized based on the spatial agglomeration density. The categories of continuous urban fabric, urban green areas, all urban infrastructures (roads, marines, airports, etc.) industrial and commercial units, and sports facilities are re-considered as concentrated urban areas. The categories of discontinuous urban fabric, dump sites, all agricultural activities, forest areas, and water lands are re-considered as extended urban areas. The categories of construction sites and sparsely vegetated areas are re-considered as differential urban areas. Furthermore, to examine the geographical proximity of AFNs and spatial density of AFIs, the spatial point density analysis is performed in ArcGIS considering the spatial locations of AFIs and (Euclidian) distance between them.

Through the analyses, the extent of AFN of cities is visualized with respect to spatial distribution and the agglomeration of AFIs associated with the urbanization moments (concentrated, extended, and differential). The results of analyses visualize and reveal the potential power of FSC of cities to be able to achieve sustainability transitions towards alternative SFSCs. Each of the FUSILLI cities is examined via GIS-based spatial analyses in the ArcGIS environment, and the cities of Rome and Oslo become prominent due to their great potential to actuate the sustainability transitions of FSCs.

4. Results

The 12 FUSILLI cities were considered in terms of the potential and portrait of their current AFIs and SFSC. Within this context, current alternative food spaces, as well as conventional food spaces, were important to empower the LFS of cities. Relying on the socio-metabolic approach, this study investigated the extent of AFNs of cities via spatial distribution of food spaces associated with urbanization moments. The flow of food as a metabolic input is comprehended via the interlinkage between production and consumption and waste management spaces. The proximity between agglomerations of food spaces and their relationship with land use (as urbanization moments) are key parameters. This interlinkage is assessed by spatial point density analysis and geoprocessing analysis regarding urbanization moments in the ArcGIS 10.8 environment. The cities with great extended AFNs are currently Rome, due to its great number of AFIs, and geographical extent of AFN covering concentrated urban as well as extended urban areas, and Oslo, due to its great variety of AFIs embedded in concentrated urban areas and has a space for alternative food production areas in its (erstwhile rural areas) extended urban areas.

Table 1 demonstrates the proximity of AFNs with the distribution of AFIs in all 12 FUSILLI cities. As seen from the thematic maps, each city represents a different dispersal over its wider geography. Each city showcases unique AFNs and geographically extends to its territory in various scales. The proximity and density of alternative food networks in cities are highly dependent on the number of AFIs and their spatial distribution extent against conventional food spaces. In this study, we showcased Rome and Oslo as

examples as they exemplify highly different contexts and dimensions. Rome is an example of a strong AFN, and Oslo is an example of a newly developing AFN with diverse AFI but still with room to be strengthened. Rome has the highest number of AFIs (more than 500) embedded in urban areas, and the most extended and dense proximity of AFN. Oslo has a developing AFN with newly established AFIs in the very center of concentrated urban areas with the highest diversity of AFIs among the FUSILLI cities.

As seen in Figure 1 of Rome, conventional consumption spaces, alternative governance spaces, and alternative consumption and alternative production spaces are agglomerated within the core of the concentrated urban area. While alternative waste management spaces are dispersed toward the edge of the concentrated urban area (including its peri-urban hinterland), and alternative production spaces, as well as alternative consumption spaces, are densely dispersed to about 860 km² towards to the edge of the concentrated urban area and towards discontinuous urban fabric and conventional agricultural lands embedded in extended urban areas of Rome. Rome is the city with the greatest potential and the highest number of AFIs within FUSILLI Cities. The majority of the AFIs are composed of community gardens; however, the other alternative food production areas, such as organic production areas, on the other hand, execute a weaker picture.

Based on the AFN mapping of Rome, not only rural areas but also urban developed areas provide “alternative zones” for developing AFN and strong urban-rural linkages in terms of AFN and SFSC against conventional systems. Besides, the path dependency for sustainability transition through AFN organization and through SFSC development, the opportunities to have more strengthened urban–peri-urban–rural linkages via alternative food spaces are observed in Rome. Moreover, Rome has a very developed food atlas. Rome has a food sovereignty potential by an average of 10% of local food production. But when considered within the metropolitan area, it goes up to 14.6% of local food production; thus, Rome has strong urban–rural linkages. With the Latium region as a hinterland area, the potential of food sovereignty is 35.5%, confirming that a food system transformation is in the making with SFSC.

Table 1. Extended alternative food geography of 12 FUSILLI cities.

FUSILLI Cities	Thematic Maps of FUSILLI Cities	FUSILLI Cities	Thematic Maps of FUSILLI Cities
Rome			

<p>Oslo</p>			
<p>Turin</p>			
<p>Kolding</p>			
<p>San Sebastian</p>			
<p>Niüfer</p>			

Figure 1. The alternative food geography of Rome and the extent of the AFN.

As seen in Figure 2 of Oslo, a huge number of conventional consumption spaces are mainly agglomerated in concentrated urban areas; however, there are also alternative production spaces, alternative consumption, and alternative waste management spaces within concentrated urban areas. Rooftop gardens, allotment gardens, and seed library are the alternative production spaces in Oslo. Alternative production spaces and alternative waste management spaces are also sparsely extended towards about 128 km² of extended urbanized areas consisting of discontinuous urban fabric, including both artificial green areas, industrial and commercial units, and towards the edge of forestry and semi-natural areas. Based on the mapping of AFN of Oslo in Figure 2, it could be said that although there are AFIs in concentrated urban areas, there is still room for alternatives to develop strong AFN and SFSC against conventional food spaces. Besides, the erstwhile rural areas should also be empowered to support AFN and zero-kilometre agriculture, and urban–rural linkage still has room to supersede the conventional agricultural areas, industrial and big-scale commercial areas embedded within extended urbanized areas.

Results of spatial analyses show that the sustainability transitions into AFN have proceeded; however, the extended urban areas (erstwhile rural areas) still have room to supersede the conventional/industrial agricultural production that it is embedded in. Further, urban–rural linkage needs to be strengthened to support the relocation of the food system in concentrated urban areas and to strengthen the rural–urban linkage for shortened FSCs. Moreover, the spatial distribution of alternative food production and procurement spaces (distribution) of the 12 cities manifests that conventional consumption spaces are agglomerated in the core of concentrated urban areas. The alternative consumption spaces, such as buyer clubs or organic bazaars, and alternative governance spaces, such as food council are agglomerated along the concentrated urban fabric, as well. On the other hand, alternative waste management spaces are extended towards the edge of concentrated urban areas. Although there are alternative production spaces within the concentrated urban fabric, such as community gardens, allotment gardens, and rooftop gardens, most of the alternative production spaces, such as organic

agriculture fields and ecovillages, are within extended urban areas towards discontinuous urban fabric and agricultural lands.

Figure 2. The alternative food geography of Oslo and the extent of the AFN.

As visualized in Figure 1, Rome city is a great example of a powerful alternative food network by having a dominant number of alternative food production spaces in both concentrated and extended urban areas. Rome also has a great portion of locally produced products in its food supply chain. Except for Rome, the cities have weaker alternative food (geography) networks in contrast to conventional agricultural lands, etc., embedded in extended urban areas. Within the context of the food supply chain of cities, we see that Oslo city is the leader with a great portion (46%) of local level (city region) food production in FSCs and is followed by Rome (40%) and Turin (38%). As seen in Figure 2, Oslo has great potential for SFSC and a local food system; however, the extended urban areas should be much more developed for alternative production initiatives to ensure the development of a more sustainable and short food production system. In terms of alternative waste management systems, Oslo has considerable initiatives.

5. Discussion

This study has a novel methodological insight by operationalizing the socio-metabolic approach to detect the “alternative zones” and to reveal the power of cities to sustain AFNs and develop SFSC. The socio-metabolic approach and planetary understanding of urbanization support us in highlighting the areas under the control of capitalist productions and operations, moreover, to detect the “alternative zones” that can be empowered for sustainability transitions in terms of all the subcategories of the alternative food system.

Building on the theoretical novelty of the socio-metabolic approach, its operationalization through the metabolic input of “food” and the specification of food via alternatives provide critical dimensions of sustainability, grassroots innovations, and circularity. To clarify, this study integrates the socio-metabolic approach, food as the

metabolic input, and a classification of alternative initiatives encompassing (1) production, (2) consumption, (3) procurement, (4) governance, and (5) waste. The combination of these contingencies offers a framework for structural analysis that addresses concerns related to sustainability, grassroots movements as food initiatives, and the circularity of the food system as a whole.

Relying on this approach, this study focuses on alternative food networks (AFNs), specifically examining the SFSC in cities by analyzing AFIs, which are sub-categorized based on their activity patterns (production, consumption, distribution, and procurement, waste management, and governance). The use of alternative food initiatives as a unit of analysis has both advantages and disadvantages. This research presupposes that “alternative food initiatives are more sustainable than conventional ones”. However, critical food studies question the legitimacy and trajectory of the contemporary food movement.

Firstly, some criticism targets neoliberal processes, arguing that food activism related to AFIs and its adherents is unwittingly complicit in neoliberal frameworks [37]. Similar critiques suggest that neoliberal tools will inevitably serve neoliberal ends, and activism exploiting gaps in the system will result in short-term practices that are eventually integrated into the system. On the other hand, a key claim in the literature on AFIs is that they represent practices that differ from conventional or industrial production–distribution, and consumption mechanisms, emphasizing concerns like ecology, health, animal welfare, and sustainability. Counter-critics argue that the basic motivations of AFIs are not distinct; rather, many alternatives are hybridized with industrial production, consumption, and distribution mechanisms. Additionally, alternatives often cannot be produced using the tools of the existing system [38]. Similarly, critiques of practices framed around localism and locality argue that “local” represents a normative scale of intervention, reducing food justice to a spatial problem. Scales are not inherently independent or spontaneous but are strategies crafted by social actors with specific agendas. Thus, a food system is not inherently more just simply because it is local. In this context, local discourse can become a “local trap” [39].

Opponents of alternative food systems argue that AFIs offer measurable contributions to the environment and the climate crisis [40]. According to Plassmann [41], initiatives encouraging best-practice management on farms achieve environmental, social, and economic gains. They also evaluate carbon footprints, estimating the climate impact of products across entire supply chains. Furthermore, AFIs contribute to rural development [23], sustainable food models [42], and broader transitions [43].

To discuss the contribution of this research to the literature, it must be emphasized that there is a lack of attempts to operationalize the socio-metabolic approach or utilize the concept of the metabolic input of food in the literature. Comprehensive searches of databases like Web of Science and Scopus using keywords such as (1) socio-metabolic approach and food geography, (2) socio-metabolic approach and alter-native food initiatives/networks, and (3) socio-metabolic approach and (urban) food systems reveal only two studies. The first study [44] applies the socio-metabolic lens and makes a substantial contribution to the field but does not attempt to operationalize the theory. The second study [45], a book composed of eight case studies, examines agriculture, soil, diets, and waste as components of local food systems within separate frames of reference. Therefore, this research contributes novel insights by combining AFIs with the socio-metabolic approach, defining proximity in AFNs, and detecting alternative zones and urban–rural interlinkages while operationalizing the theory of the socio-metabolic approach.

Although the use of AFNs and AFIs as the unit of the analysis is a limitation of this study considering the discussion above, this research opened a new window into practical

implications for implementing food policies in European cities. The spatial results and analysis developed through the methodology of this manuscript transparently reveals the gaps and the potential in the cities for supporting the development of AFNs and for promoting the transitions through SFSCs. For instance, the cities of Tampere and San Sebastian have great potential to implement “city–region food system” (CRFS) policy, which paves the way for SFSCs; however, Tampere lacks alternative consumer initiatives and San Sebastian’s agri-food production is primarily dominated by industrial agricultural production. Similarly, Athens has strong links with its rural hinterland, but the food produced in Athens is not locally consumed, and the city lacks policies and implications through alternative consumption practices. However, Athens is also a case where a developing AFI in a core urban area diminishes “food deserts” the most among all other cities [46]. Turin, as a specific case, not only includes alternative consumption initiatives in the concentrated urban areas but also in the extended urban areas, which express the multifunctionality of rural areas are more powerful, and the conventional consumption spaces are not relatively dense. As another case, Nilüfer, the district of the metropolitan city of Bursa, Turkey, and the urban core of the city, has strong links with rural and agricultural production, but the number of the initiatives seem limited. It shows the deficiencies of capacity, quality, and organizational implications are weak and must be strengthened for the potential of the CRFS and SFSC.

The examples and cases might be multiplied in the scope of this research and its findings under the limits of this manuscript. However, this research only handles European context and European cities. When the food, agriculture, and sustainability transitions issues are considered, geographical context, scale, societal structure, historical background, and many other contingencies profoundly affect the systemic change and, therefore, the possibilities through sustainability transitions. This research is limited to the European context with a specific limitation of 12 FUSILLI cities, and it is crucial to implement the methodological approach in different contexts to see the consistency of the results. As another limitation, the very nature of AFIs makes data gathering a sprawled and blurry process, which primarily results in the use of secondary sources. In the meantime, the use of CORINE as an open-sourced general secondary data and the lack of local spatial and demographic data are deficiencies of this research.

6. Conclusions

This study serves to reveal the current moment of transformation into a more sustainable food system and the development of SFSC in FUSILLI cities. The results of the research provide a horizon for designing specific policies and actions for SFSC. While doing so, the conceptualization we used to express the contradictions between the capitalist mode of urban development (planetary mode of urbanization as concentrated and extended urbanization) and alternative bottom-up spatial development (rural, powerful urban–rural linkages) in association with AFIs.

As a primary practical implication to support SFSC in cities, we must strengthen urban–rural linkages. However, each city and settlement has its own unique conditions and even 12 FUSILLI cities do not have the same interrelations with nearby (erstwhile) rural areas. So, the ultimate mission of this study within its limits can only be to identify gaps and potentials of AFNs in FUSILLI cities to fulfill a specific urban food plan for SFSC in each city. This study contributes to this framework by revealing the potential and deficiencies of cities for SFSC. Strengthened rural–urban linkages cannot only foster AFN and SFSC but also ensure food and nutrition security through promoting opportunities for rural and urban producers and consumers to derive greater value from integrated land use, natural resources, and circular economy across territories, promoting income-generating opportunities on and off-farm particularly geared towards women and youth,

including social and solidarity economy; or boost-ing rural–urban public partnerships for preserving natural heritage.

Since food is one of the globally traded products and a vast majority of rural areas are served by industrial, agricultural production, there is a need to reveal this contradiction between rural and extended urbanization areas, and we need to support rural as the place of local food production with strong policies of SFSC. Moreover, the spatial analyses of cities provide an atlas of AFN, potentials of relocation of the food systems, potentials for the development of new nested markets, potentials for extended SFSC, and provide an atlas of the gaps, deficiencies, and problems within the urban food systems in 12 FUSILLI cities. So, it is obvious that the sustainability transitions through SFSC have proceeded, but rural areas still have room to supersede the conventional/industrial agricultural production embedded in extended urban areas. It is the same for urban–rural linkages, which need to be strengthened to support the relocation of the food system in (concentrated) urban areas. Furthermore, the spatial distribution of alternative food production and procurement spaces (distribution) manifests that conventional consumption spaces are dominantly agglomerated in the core of concentrated urban areas. It is obvious that FUSILLI cities should support civic food initiatives such as consumer cooperatives, box schemes, and farmers’ markets, as well as developing new governance mechanisms, such as food councils and food courts, and developing novel sustainable waste management systems.

As examined in different European cities with various sizes and populations, it is seen that conventional consumption and production spaces are still dominant activities in both concentrated and extended urban areas within the mainstream FSC of these cities. The local interlinkage between urban and rural (concentrated and extended) areas is still weak to sustain an SFSC and an extended AFN except for Italian cities (as seen in Rome and Turin, as partners of the project). Italy has had a great effort and solidarity in creating AFN in cities for about a half-century. These results give us important inputs for policy and action development for sustainability transitions through SFSC in cities. Not only FUSILLI cities but also European cities are dependent upon industrial unsustainable agro-food production; they have lost links between urban and rural, and the sustainability transitions in agro-food system is a long-ranged solidarity struggle.

This study will help future studies to benefit from the socio-metabolic approach in sustainability transitions studies. Future studies should develop our operational approach focusing on food or other metabolic inputs/outputs to detect the power of the local dimension for sustainability transitions. As we use CORINE spatial data in the European context, further reconceptualization of urban land use is needed based on the availability of local spatial data. Besides, detailed studies are needed in the future, focusing on very local contexts to examine the contextual dynamics and differences of alternative (food) networks for sustainability transitions.

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